

Promotion of Women Empowerment through ICT

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Introduction

“Countries and Nations which do not respect women have never become great nor will even be in future” – Swami Vivekananda

Our nation has the rich heritage of empowering women in every possible dimension, over the years, through social and political reforms. The National Commission for Women was established under the Act of Parliament in 1990, in order to assure the fundamental and legal rights entitled to womenfolk. The 73rd and 74th Amendments (1993) to the Constitution of India state about the provision and participation of women in local government bodies – the panchayats and municipalities for the confirmation of equity of women in decision making. The Indian National Policy for the Empowerment of Women (2001) highlights the action-plans towards women equality. The ever-growing efforts on women empowerment was fueled by sustained initiatives across the globe as illustrated by the following:

- The Convention on Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination Against Women (CEDAW) [1993]
- The Mexico Plan of Action [1975]
- Nairobi Forward Looking Strategies [1985]
- Beijing Declaration [1995]
- The Platform for Action (1995)

The alarming rate of increase in the domestic, social, political and economical injustice against women and its manifestation on this marginalized sector reiterate on the demand to formulate newer strategies and solutions, to achieve women empowerment, which is the pathway of sustained development and prosperity of any nation. Though the population of women in the global scenario is about 50%, it has steeply declined in India due to the discriminated attitude towards this under-privileged gender. The social and cultural systems and practices of our country pushed the women behind, without giving the due recognition and respect to them. The social and political reforms staged by the national leaders paved ways to reinstall the rights and respect of women.

According to the UN India Business Form (UNIBF), the women should be provided essential training and opportunities, to empower them educationally, financially, professionally and technologically.

Gender Action Plan (GAP) - 2018-2021 targets at advancing gender equity and the rights of women and girls. Its primary mandate is to realize the rights of the children. It aims to achieve Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) in the light of women empowerment.

Role of Ict

ICT is proved to a vital tool through which women gain confidence and self-reliance. The digital awakening on women empowerment is mirrored through hundreds of blogs, websites and newsletters hosted on the internet. The advent of Information and Communication Technology has a phenomenal impact on women empowerment. through literacy, networking, skill development to attain technological, social, political and economic empowerment at local, national and global level.

Information and Communication Technologies (ICT)

ICT is an outgrowth of computer technologies that provides enormous platforms and services for creation, transformation, communication and distribution of information, with the support of essential hardware and software, internet being its backbone.

World Summit on the Information Society (WSIS)

There is a sharp awakening on across the nations to leverage ICT to empower the women through ICT and its allied services. The United Nation's WSIS was one of the pioneering efforts toward Women Empowerment through ICT.

The Geneva Summit held in 2003, aimed to develop political will and to establish the foundations for an Information Society for all. In total, 175 Governments endorsed the Declaration of Principles and Plan of Action at the first phase. The second phase of WSIS is planned for November 2005 in Tunis. In 1996, the Division for the Advancement of Women, in collaboration with United Nations and NGO partners, organized an Expert Group Meeting on "Global Information through Computer Networking Technology in the Follow-Up to the Fourth World Conference on Women". The Division also published an issue of women 2000 entitled, "Women and the Information Revolution". 27. A "Canon on Gender Partnerships and ICT Development", developed primarily by women participants at the first international conference on ICT, the Global Knowledge Partnership Conference in 1997, outlined key principles for the development and design of ICT, prioritizing equal participation and gender-aware assessments and evaluations of ICT projects and programmes. 28

At the second Global Knowledge Partnership Conference held three years later, a specific Women's Forum developed a comprehensive set of recommendations. 29

The major recommendations included:

- Mainstreaming and monitoring of a gender perspective in all ICT initiatives;
- Collecting sex disaggregated data on the use of ICT and women's participation in policy-making as well as developing targets, indicators and benchmarks to track the progress of women's and girl's access to the benefits of ICT;
- Identifying and promoting good practices and lessons learned on the ways women and girls are using ICT;
- Capacity-building towards gender equality in education and employment;
- Enhancing democracy and women's participation through electronic connectivity; and
- Developing research and policies on health and environmental hazards of ICT industries

A Few Governmental and Non-Governmental Empowerments

There are hundreds of empowerment strategies rolled out by the governmental and non-governmental agencies which aim at educating, skilling, training and empowering the women and girls. A few illustrations are:

- SMILE (Savitri Marketing Institutions for Ladies Empowerment) conducts IT Seminars and Training and Computer Literacy Programmes for the age group of 6 – 60.
- SEWA (Self-Employed Women's Association), to network and get connected to the peer-group
- Ujjas Innovation: The Newsletter to bring out the issues of women
- The Dhan Foundation and Swayam Krishi Sangam: Empowerment of marginalized women through ICT

A numerous websites on women empowerment are available on-line, with a set of specific objectives and functions; Few of such websites are

Conclusion

The wide-spread awakening and the result-oriented action plans of governmental/ non-governmental agencies are expected to bring up visible and perceived changes in the empowerment of women. Despite these efforts, there are instances on gender-inequality; gender-disparity and gender-bias incidents are reported in from birth to death.

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